

1 **The path towards a unified trait space: synthesizing plant functional diversity**

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14 **Summary**

15 Plant traits capture the remarkable diversity of ecological strategies, yet synthesizing this
16 complexity into coherent frameworks remains challenging. Trait spaces have significantly
17 advanced this effort, distilling numerous traits into meaningful ecological dimensions. Recent
18 frameworks integrate above- and belowground characteristics, but other dimensions—such as
19 reproduction, phenology, hydraulics, and mycorrhizal associations—remain poorly
20 represented, facing conceptual and methodological hurdles. Resolving these issues requires
21 addressing biases in trait databases, standardizing methodologies, and integrating complex or
22 categorical traits. In this review, we propose the development of a fully unified trait space
23 that is flexible, modular, and scalable, which would greatly enhance global comparisons,
24 improve our predictive capabilities of plant ecological responses to global change, and
25 ultimately strengthen biodiversity monitoring and management.

26 **Resumen (SPANISH)**

27 Los rasgos de las plantas recogen la extraordinaria diversidad de estrategias ecológicas, pero
28 sintetizar esta complejidad en marcos coherentes es complicado. El uso de espacios sintéticos
29 basados rasgos ha supuesto un avance decisivo, al reducir la multitud de rasgos a
30 dimensiones ecológicas con significado. Algunos avances recientes han integrado
31 características aéreas y subterráneas, aunque otras dimensiones —como la reproducción, la
32 fenología, la hidráulica o las asociaciones micorrízicas— permanecen poco representadas y
33 afrontan obstáculos conceptuales y metodológicos. Superar estas limitaciones requiere
34 corregir sesgos en las bases de datos, estandarizar las metodologías e incorporar rasgos
35 complejos o de naturaleza categórica. En esta revisión proponemos el desarrollo de un
36 espacio de rasgos plenamente unificado, flexible, modular y escalable, que permita mejorar
37 las comparaciones a escala global, reforzar la capacidad predictiva sobre las respuestas
38 ecológicas de las plantas al cambio global y, en última instancia, fortalecer el seguimiento y
39 la gestión de la biodiversidad.

40 **Sommario (ITALIAN)**

41 Tramite la misura di tratti funzionali è possibile catturare la straordinaria complessità di
42 strategie ecologiche presenti nella vegetazione; tuttavia, come riassumere questa complessità
43 in modelli coerenti, rimane ancora una sfida. Gli spazi funzionali hanno fornito un contributo
44 fondamentale a questo sforzo, aiutando a riassumere i numerosi tratti disponibili in un
45 numero ridotto di dimensioni ecologicamente significative. Studi recenti sono riusciti a
46 riassumere numerosi tratti legati ad organi aerei e radicali delle piante, ma molti altri aspetti
47 come riproduzione, fenologia, idraulica e mutualismo restano scarsamente rappresentate a
48 causa di limitazioni concettuali e metodologiche relative alla loro integrazione. Per risolvere
49 queste problematiche è necessario affrontare gli squilibri presenti dei database dei tratti, così

50 come standardizzare le metodologie di analisi ed integrare tratti complessi o categorici non
51 rappresentati. In questa review, proponiamo lo sviluppo di uno spazio funzionale unificato,
52 flessibile, modulare e scalabile, capace di potenziare i paragoni tra specie a scala globale e di
53 migliorare le previsioni sulle risposte ecologiche delle specie ai cambiamenti globali,
54 rafforzando le basi per il monitoraggio e la gestione della biodiversità.

55 **Kokkuvõte (ESTONIAN)**

56 Taimetunnustes on kajastatud ökoloogiliste strateegiate märkimisväärne elurikkus, kuid selle
57 mitmekesisuse sünteesimine sidusateks raamistikeks on endiselt keeruline. Tunnusruumid on
58 seda protsessi oluliselt lihtsustanud, taandades arvukad taimetunnused tähenduslikeks
59 ökoloogilisteks mõõtmeks. Hiljutised uurimistööd on ühendanud taimede maapealsed ja
60 maa-alused tunnused ühtsesse raamistikku, kuid mitmed teised taime omadused – nagu
61 paljunemine, fenoloogia, hüdraulika ja mükoriisa seosed – on endiselt halvasti esindatud
62 kontseptuaalsete ja metoodiliste takistuste tõttu. Nende probleemide lahendamine nõuab
63 tunnuste andmebaaside ühtlustamist, metoodikate standardiseerimist ning keerukate või
64 kategooriliste tunnuste integreerimist. Selles ülevaates tutvustame, kuidas luua täielikult
65 kokku koondatud tunnusruum, mis on paindlik, modulaarne ja skaleeritav. See edendaks
66 oluliselt globaalseid võrdlusi, aitaks paremini prognoosida globaalmuutuste mõju taimedele
67 ning soodustaks lõpptulemusena ka elurikkuse seiret ja hooldamist.

68 **Keywords:** functional traits; trait space; trait dimensionality; plant strategies; above-
69 belowground integration; reproductive traits; phenology; mycorrhizal associations

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73 **Contents list**

74	Summary	2
75	I. Introduction	4
76	II. Recent advances in trait spaces	5
77	III. Incorporating additional functional dimensions	5
78	IV. Challenges, open questions, and future directions	8
79	V. Conclusions	10
80	Acknowledgements	11
81	References	11

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84 I. Introduction

85 Plants vary immensely in how they capture sunlight, use water, store carbon, reproduce, and
86 decompose. This diversity stems from their traits—measurable characteristics that shape
87 plant growth, reproduction, and survival—defining how plants respond to the environment
88 and influence ecosystem functions (de Bello *et al.*, 2021). Ecologists use a vast array of
89 traits, as highlighted in the TRY database, which currently defines over 2,000 distinct traits,
90 exemplifying the potential and complexity of trait-based ecology. While this trait diversity
91 provides a powerful framework for understanding plant strategies, the sheer number and
92 varied application of traits across studies challenges synthesis and limit comparability.
93 Moreover, because plant phenotypes consist of coordinated sets of traits (Fig. 1), focusing on
94 individual traits may overlook essential aspects of whole-plant function (Carmona, 2023;
95 Díaz, 2025).

96 Trait spaces offer a framework to distil complex trait data into fewer, meaningful dimensions,
97 capturing species' functional strategies (Mouillot *et al.*, 2021). By leveraging trait
98 correlations, these frameworks synthesise plant phenotypes, allowing comparisons of whole-
99 plant strategies, improving ecological interpretation and offering scalable insights into
100 biodiversity patterns and ecosystem processes. Trait-space thinking has progressively
101 enriched ecology: Grime (1974) positioned species within a triangular space of competition,
102 stress tolerance, and ruderality; Westoby (1998) formalised orthogonal axes of leaf
103 investment, size and regenerative capacity; and the leaf economics spectrum (LES; Wright *et al.*,
104 2004) uncovered a global fast–slow continuum in leaf physiology. Building on these
105 foundations, recent syntheses coupling above- and belowground traits show that strategy
106 variation spans the whole plant (Díaz *et al.*, 2016; Carmona *et al.*, 2021a; Weigelt *et al.*,
107 2021).

108 Nonetheless, key challenges persist, including integrating underrepresented functional
109 dimensions, addressing biases in trait data, and standardizing methods. A truly unified trait
110 space would enhance the comparability, coherence, and scalability of ecological insights,
111 offering applications from remote-sensing-based biodiversity monitoring to forecasting
112 ecosystem responses to global change. Here we review recent advances, highlight ongoing
113 challenges, and outline future directions toward achieving a unified plant trait space.

114 **II. Recent advances in trait spaces**

115 Recent developments in trait spaces have reshaped plant functional ecology. Díaz et al.
116 (2016) introduced the global spectrum of plant form and function (GSPFF), defining a
117 primary axis of plant size—from tall, large-seeded, dense-wooded species to small, light-
118 stemmed ones—and a second axis contrasting acquisitive versus conservative leaf
119 economies. Bergmann et al. (2020) expanded trait synthesis belowground with the root
120 economics spectrum, identifying two key dimensions for fine-root traits: one contrasting
121 thicker, mycorrhizal-dependent roots with thinner roots adapted for independent nutrient
122 uptake, and another reflecting resource acquisition and conservation strategies.

123 Integrating above- and belowground perspectives has sparked debates over trait
124 dimensionality and coordination. Carmona et al., (2021) proposed a unified plant functional
125 space (UPFS) combining root and shoot traits into a four-dimensional space, highlighting
126 partial independence between above- and belowground strategies. Conversely, Weigelt et al.
127 (2021) proposed that leaf and root economic traits align along a single dimension. Bueno et
128 al. (2023) suggested that these conflicting conclusions arose from interpretative differences
129 rather than trait selection or ordination methods, emphasizing the need to explore covariation
130 beyond pairwise comparisons. These discrepancies signal that, beyond pairwise loadings,
131 robust tools are needed to probe covariation in high-dimensional spaces. Beccari & Carmona
132 (2024) introduced such tools: using angular metrics and effective-dimensionality tests, they
133 confirmed the independence of leaf and root economic axes and revealed a single whole-plant
134 size dimension. While aligning with Weigelt et al. (2021) in emphasizing the independence of
135 root size from root economics, the study also pointed to other factors influencing the debate,
136 such as the overrepresentation of plants of the Northern hemisphere (Maitner *et al.*, 2023),
137 which may shape trait-space structure and highlight the need for a more balanced species
138 representation in global syntheses.

139 **III. Incorporating additional functional dimensions**

140 Despite substantial recent advances in trait spaces, key conceptual and methodological
141 challenges persist, particularly in integrating historically underrepresented functions with
142 sparser data or more complex statistical properties. Incorporating reproductive, phenological,
143 hydraulic, metabolic, and mycorrhizal traits could substantially enhance our understanding of
144 plant ecological strategies. However, each of these aspects introduces unique complexities
145 that remain largely unresolved.

146 While pace-of-life and reproductive strategies are the main two dimensions of life history
147 both for plants and animals (Salguero-Gómez et al., 2016; Beccari et al., 2024), reproduction
148 has been largely overlooked in plant trait spaces. Recent frameworks highlight trade-offs
149 between floral investment and maintenance driven by pollinator and abiotic factors (Roddy et
150 al., 2021). However, it remains unclear whether reproductive traits represent dimensions
151 independent of those already captured in the UPFS. For instance, in Central European forbs,
152 reproductive traits form a dimension separate from leaf economics and plant size (E-Vojtkó et
153 al., 2022), whereas floral traits in woody species correlate with both dimensions (Paż-
154 Dyerska & Jagodziński, 2024). Additionally, a distinct 'clonal trait space' has been proposed
155 for perennial herbs, reflecting persistence and stress tolerance (Chelli et al., 2024). However,
156 the potential to include clonality in a hypothetical unified space is limited because it would
157 lead to a space where many species cluster into a limited region. Methodological and
158 conceptual challenges, including trait measurement standardization and managing context-
159 dependent and categorical traits (Klimešová et al., 2025), must be addressed to fully
160 integrate reproductive traits into a comprehensive trait space.

161 Phenological traits, such as timing of leaf-out, flowering, and fruiting, shape species
162 interactions, resource partitioning, and ecosystem processes (Cleland & Wolkovich, 2024).
163 Yet, phenology is not integrated into global trait frameworks. Leaf phenology partially aligns
164 with the leaf economics spectrum, with deciduous species typically adopting fast, acquisitive
165 strategies and evergreens exhibiting slow, conservative strategies (González-M. et al., 2021).
166 Nonetheless, phenological traits often capture unique temporal niches and strategies
167 independent of or complementary to other trait dimensions (Körner & Basler, 2010).
168 Although recent studies have quantified various phenological characteristics, comprehensive
169 attempts to define explicit phenological trait spaces remain limited, reflecting substantial
170 methodological and conceptual challenges (Pau et al., 2011). The circular nature of
171 phenological data—January is temporally closer to December than to June— which
172 complicates conventional linear trait analyses, and the inherent plasticity and context-
173 dependence of phenological traits hinder their integration into trait spaces (Palacio et al.,
174 2025).

175 Plant hydraulic traits—including xylem vulnerability to embolism, hydraulic conductivity,
176 and anatomical features such as vessel size and density—underpin species' survival during
177 drought and influence biogeographic distributions along moisture gradients (Liu et al., 2019;

178 Laughlin *et al.*, 2020; González-M. *et al.*, 2021). Global-scale analyses have proposed a
179 'wood economics' trait space structured around trade-offs between hydraulic safety (embolism
180 resistance) and efficiency (water transport capacity), although empirical support for a
181 universal trade-off is mixed, suggesting multiple independent dimensions may exist (Chave
182 *et al.*, 2009; Liu *et al.*, 2019). The extent to which hydraulic traits align with dimensions
183 already represented in the UPFS remains unclear: hydraulic traits often correlate with plant
184 size, reflecting coordination between height and hydraulic architecture (Liu *et al.*, 2019);
185 however, they show limited alignment with the leaf economics spectrum, highlighting their
186 potential to represent distinct, complementary dimensions (Li *et al.*, 2015; González-M. *et*
187 *al.*, 2021). Although stem wood density broadly correlates with embolism resistance, it fails
188 to capture the full range of hydraulic strategies—especially the contrast between angiosperms
189 and conifers shown by Laughlin *et al.* (2020)—so incorporating direct hydraulic traits is
190 likely to expand the dimensionality of the UPFS. In addition, initial measurements suggest
191 that root hydraulic conductance and embolism resistance do not always mirror stem traits,
192 hinting at a below-ground axis of drought adaptation that remains largely unsampled
193 (Carminati & Javaux, 2020). Integrating hydraulic traits presents methodological and
194 conceptual challenges, including measurement complexity, methodological variability, and
195 limited data coverage, particularly for non-woody species, which often lack standardized
196 hydraulic metrics.

197 Mycorrhizal traits (*sensu* Chaudhary *et al.*, 2022, focusing here on plant-level and symbiotic
198 metrics such as mycorrhizal type and colonisation intensity) shape nutrient acquisition,
199 growth strategies, and ecosystem processes like carbon and nutrient cycling (Tedersoo *et al.*,
200 2020). Recent global analyses suggest partial alignment between mycorrhizal traits and
201 several dimensions of the UPFS. First, arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) and ectomycorrhizal
202 (EM) associations often differ systematically in economic traits: EM plants typically exhibit
203 conservative strategies with low leaf and root nutrient concentrations and high tissue density,
204 while AM plants generally show more acquisitive traits potentially aligned with the leaf and
205 root economics spectrum (Averill *et al.*, 2019). Second, EM plants largely correspond to
206 woody lineages, whereas AM plants span a broader range of growth forms, including both
207 small herbs and tall trees, indirectly correlating mycorrhizal type with the size dimension.
208 Third, EM and AM plants also differ along the root economics spectrum, especially in
209 morphological traits like root diameter and specific root length (Weigelt *et al.*, 2021).
210 Nonetheless, mycorrhizal type alone does not fully determine plant trait syndromes, as

211 species within both AM and EM types span substantial trait variation. Empirical evidence
212 indicates that mycorrhizal traits capture unique aspects in resource-acquisition strategies and
213 symbiotic reliance that are not fully represented by existing trait dimensions (Weigelt *et al.*,
214 2021), suggesting that explicitly including mycorrhizal traits could add valuable dimensions
215 to current functional trait spaces. Integrating these traits poses additional methodological and
216 conceptual challenges, particularly because mycorrhizal associations involve both plant and
217 fungal partners, and many mycorrhizal traits are categorical or context-dependent. Systematic
218 integration, rather than aggregation for its own sake, is therefore essential. Further
219 complexity arises because colonization intensity—a promising continuous trait—uses
220 inherently different metrics for EM (% root tips colonized) versus AM (% root length
221 colonized), limiting comparability across types. The development of novel standardized
222 metrics reflecting symbiotic flexibility or status might offer practical pathways toward
223 incorporating these critical traits into unified frameworks.

224 Other promising functional dimensions, such as the plant metabolome, capturing a vast array
225 of biochemical investments (Sardans *et al.*, 2011), or carbon allocation patterns, reflecting
226 critical strategies for resource uptake and storage (Freschet *et al.*, 2018), remain largely
227 absent from current synthetic trait frameworks. Future expansions of the UPFS could
228 incorporate these traits, further deepening our understanding of plant strategies and their
229 responses to global environmental change.

230 **IV. Challenges, open questions, and future directions**

231 Trait databases exhibit significant geographic, phylogenetic, and functional biases. Temperate
232 regions, woody species, and common taxa are disproportionately represented, while tropical
233 and subtropical regions, herbaceous species, and specialized forms like epiphytes or
234 succulents remain underrepresented (Kattge *et al.*, 2020). This imbalance can skew our
235 understanding of trait correlations and functional space occupancy (Fig. 2), potentially
236 overlooking intermediate growth forms like shrubs (Barajas Barbosa *et al.*, 2023).

237 Addressing these biases requires coordinated international initiatives, such as targeted trait
238 collection campaigns in understudied biomes and taxa (Laughlin, 2024). Collaborations and
239 capacity-building programs can encourage data contributions from underrepresented and
240 megadiverse regions, enhancing database comprehensiveness. In the short term, adjusting
241 trait sampling efforts or analyses to reflect the true proportions of growth forms at relevant

242 scales could help achieve a more accurate representation of plant functional diversity
243 (Barajas Barbosa *et al.*, 2023).

244 Data sparsity is another critical limitation, especially as the number of considered traits
245 increases, making it difficult to fully characterize many species (Díaz *et al.*, 2016; Carmona
246 *et al.*, 2021a). Trait imputation approaches, such as missForest or Bayesian hierarchical
247 models, offer a promising way to mitigate these gaps, enabling a fuller exploitation of
248 existing trait databases (Stewart *et al.*, 2023). However, imputed values should be used
249 cautiously, as their accuracy depends on the structure of the available empirical data (Gorné
250 *et al.*, 2025). In parallel, remote sensing (e.g., hyperspectral imaging for leaf traits, LiDAR
251 for height; Castro Sánchez-Bermejo *et al.*, 2023) and the automated extraction of leaf size and
252 shape from millions of digitised herbarium specimens via deep-learning pipelines (Daru,
253 2025), offer efficient and scalable methods for collecting trait data across broad spatial scales.
254 Integrating these technological advances with traditional ground-based measurements can
255 enhance the density and coverage of trait information, improving understanding of trait
256 distributions (Beccari *et al.*, 2024b).

257 Methodological inconsistencies, including variability in trait definitions, measurement
258 methods, and study conditions (e.g., field vs. greenhouse) undermine comparability.
259 International collaborations must develop and disseminate standardized measurement
260 protocols, including clear definitions, methodologies, and data-integration guidelines (Pérez-
261 Harguindeguy *et al.*, 2013; Freschet *et al.*, 2021). Harmonizing these protocols will
262 substantially improve comparability and facilitate robust global analyses.

263 Integrating non-standard traits such as cyclical phenological traits or categorical traits (e.g.,
264 mycorrhizal associations) poses methodological challenges that traditional PCA-based trait
265 spaces struggle to address. Trait spaces derived from dissimilarity metrics (e.g., via PCoA or
266 NMDS) effectively accommodate these diverse trait types (Mouillot *et al.*, 2021), but suffer
267 from instability, as adding new species or traits requires recalculating the entire space,
268 altering previously established species positions. A promising solution is to map these
269 complex traits onto an existing, stable trait space without explicitly incorporating them as
270 additional dimensions (Carmona *et al.*, 2021b; Pavanetto *et al.*, 2024). This approach
271 maintains trait space comparability while enriching ecological interpretation (Box 1).

272 Determining how many dimensions adequately represent global plant functional diversity
273 involves balancing parsimony—keeping trait spaces interpretable and applicable—and

274 ecological realism—capturing the complexity of plant strategies. The choice of how to
275 address dimensionality depends heavily on the research question. A common approach
276 involves identifying a discrete number of dimensions to represent the diversity of functions
277 across species and communities (Mouillot *et al.*, 2021; Carmona *et al.*, 2021a).
278 Alternatively, rather than fixing the number of dimensions, a more refined estimation of how
279 much new ecological information each additional trait contributes can offer important
280 insights into whether a new set of traits meaningfully expands the trait space. This also
281 enables comparisons of the influence that individual traits have in shaping plant strategies. A
282 useful approach in these cases consists of estimating the effective number of dimensions of a
283 trait space through the evenness of PCA eigenvalues (Beccari & Carmona, 2024), which can
284 be enhanced by integrating trait networks (Li & He, 2024) with ordination to address
285 modularity (Box 2).

286 Embracing modularity—allowing researchers to selectively integrate trait dimensions based
287 on specific questions (Carmona *et al.*, 2021b,a)—could effectively balance complexity with
288 interpretability. Such an approach is particularly useful when certain traits are relevant only to
289 subsets of species, preventing non-applicable species from collapsing into meaningless
290 regions of trait space. Modularity thus facilitates comparisons while accommodating context-
291 dependent, categorical, or specialized traits, creating a flexible, scalable framework adaptable
292 to diverse ecological analyses (see Box 1 for a modular roadmap).

293 **V. Conclusions**

294 The pursuit of a unified trait space holds tremendous potential to transform how we
295 understand, predict, and manage plant diversity and ecosystem function. By synthesizing the
296 complexity of plant traits into a coherent and broadly applicable framework, this approach
297 can substantially enhance comparability and generalizability across studies, enabling scalable
298 insights from local to global scales.

299 Once a robust unified trait space is established, leveraging its power will enable innovative
300 analytical approaches capable of characterizing and comparing patterns of functional
301 structure. Probabilistic frameworks (Carmona *et al.*, 2021b) offer detailed quantitative
302 descriptions of species and community occupancy within trait spaces. Such approaches have
303 the potential to uncover complex associations between functional structure, environmental
304 gradients, and ecosystem functioning, enhancing predictive capabilities and deepening our
305 understanding of ecological processes.

306 Ultimately, describing a unified plant trait space is less about reaching a destination than
307 about continuously making the path as we walk. Echoing Antonio Machado's sentiment—
308 "Caminante, no hay camino, se hace camino al andar" (Traveler, there is no path, the path is
309 made by walking)—each successful mapping of functional space will inevitably prompt
310 further exploration. Though inherently incomplete, striving toward a unified trait space
311 promises substantial rewards: a common, scalable framework for biodiversity monitoring,
312 anticipating ecological responses to climate change, guiding conservation efforts, and
313 refining ecosystem modelling. Embracing this unified vision will foster deeper ecological
314 understanding, enhanced predictive power, and ultimately more effective environmental
315 stewardship.

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322 **Data availability**

323 The data used in this study were obtained from the TRY plant trait database ([https://www.try-](https://www.try-db.org)
324 [db.org](https://www.try-db.org)) and are freely available following TRY standard request procedure.

325 **Author contributions**

326 Both authors contributed to the conceptualization of the manuscript. C.P.C. wrote the first
327 draft, which was subsequently edited and commented on by E.B.

328 **Competing interests**

329 None declared.

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483 Fig. 1. Schematic representation of broad groups of traits measurable across plant organs.
484 Capturing the diversity of plant functions requires considering a comprehensive set of traits
485 describing how plants allocate resources across their entire phenotype. Each group
486 corresponds to traits associated with specific plant functions or components: life-history
487 traits, relating to species' pace of life and reproductive strategies (e.g., growth rate, longevity,
488 reproductive frequency, fecundity); canopy traits, describing crown architecture (e.g.,
489 maximum crown width); metabolic traits, reflecting chemical composition (e.g., C, P, N
490 content); seed traits, describing seed morphology and physiology (e.g., seed mass, seed
491 shape); hydraulic traits, related to water transport and drought response (e.g., turgor loss
492 point); wood traits, associated with structural support and defence (e.g., woodiness, bark
493 thickness); phenological traits, describing timing of life-cycle events (e.g., flowering time,
494 deciduousness); clonal traits, capturing vegetative reproduction potential (e.g., clonal ability,
495 bud bank size); root traits, reflecting structural support and resource acquisition by coarse
496 roots (e.g., rooting depth, lateral spread); fine-root traits, related to resource uptake efficiency
497 (e.g., specific root length, root diameter); mycorrhizal traits, indicating type and intensity of
498 mycorrhizal symbioses (e.g., mycorrhizal type, colonization intensity); flower traits, floral

499 morpho-physiological characteristics (e.g., flower size, nectar production); leaf traits, leaf
500 morpho-physiological characteristics (e.g., leaf area, leaf nitrogen content); and whole-plant
501 traits, integrating across organs (e.g., plant height). Illustration by Luís Gustavo Barretto
502 Rodrigues.

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504

505 Fig. 2. Effect of database biases on species distributions within trait space. Trait spaces were
506 constructed using traits from the global spectrum of plant form and function (GSPFF; Díaz et
507 al., 2016) and comparing two versions of the TRY database (Kattge *et al.*, 2020): (a) version
508 3 (earlier, less complete: based on 1,308 species) and (b) version 6 (more recent; 3,045
509 species). Each trait space was generated using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), with
510 axes representing the main gradients of trait variation: the first component corresponds to
511 plant size (small herbaceous species on the left, large woody species on the right), and the
512 second component reflects the leaf economics spectrum. Trait loadings on PCA axes are
513 shown as arrows, and percentages indicate variance explained by each component. Species'
514 probabilistic distributions are visualized with contour lines at 50% (inner) and 99% (outer)
515 thresholds; darker regions indicate higher species density. Marginal density plots illustrate
516 species distributions along primary axes: the top plots correspond to the size gradient, and the
517 side plots (left in a, right in b) correspond to the leaf economics spectrum. Blue lines
518 represent herbaceous species, orange lines represent woody species, and dotted lines show
519 combined densities. TRY version 3 was notably biased toward woody species (73.2%
520 woody), lacking representation of herbaceous strategies. In contrast, TRY version 6 provided
521 improved trait coverage and more balanced representation (56.6% woody), leading to a more
522 balanced coverage of trait space, especially capturing herbaceous strategies more completely.

523 **Box 1: A modular roadmap for unifying plant trait spaces**

524 To resolve debates on trait dimensionality and integration, we propose a modular framework
525 for a unified plant functional trait space. This approach builds on a stable core derived from
526 widely available traits, which is then extended with flexible, add-on modules. This design
527 ensures consistency and comparability across diverse studies while allowing adaptation to
528 specific research questions, ecosystems, or data limitations.

529 Core space: We propose to anchor the space in traits known to be related to two primary
530 dimensions: (1) a plant size gradient (e.g., height, stem density, rooting depth) reflecting
531 variation in structural investment; and (2) a resource economics spectrum, which contrasts
532 fast-growing, resource-acquisitive strategies with slow-growing, conservative ones.

533 Depending on the specific aims (e.g., focusing only on aboveground components or assessing
534 whole-plant phenotypes), the resource economics spectrum should include traits that
535 acknowledge the partial independence between leaf and root traits (Carmona *et al.*, 2021a;
536 Weigelt *et al.*, 2021). These axes can be generated via principal component analysis (PCA)
537 on standardized traits.

538 Modular extensions: For broader coverage, module traits (e.g., hydraulics, phenology,
539 mycorrhizal, or others) can be incorporated into the core dataset. If traits are continuous, the
540 PCA can be recalculated and changes assessed using the effective number of dimensions
541 (Beccari & Carmona, 2024); significance can be tested through randomizations of the
542 module traits. Challenging traits, such as categorical mycorrhizal types or clonality, or
543 circular phenological data, can be mapped onto the core space instead. This approach
544 explores how groups (e.g., AM vs. EM species, early- vs. late-flowering guilds) differ in
545 occupation, revealing complementary patterns without forcing recalculation (Pavanetto *et*
546 *al.*, 2024). These alternatives boost flexibility while addressing methodological hurdles like
547 context-dependence or data inconsistencies (de Bello *et al.*, 2025).

548

549 **Box 2: Integrating trait networks and ordination for modular trait spaces**

550 Trait networks uncover how plant traits interconnect, moving beyond simple bivariate plots to
551 map the web of relationships that shape plant strategies (Messier *et al.*, 2017; He *et al.*,
552 2020). A trait network treats the phenotype as a graph whose nodes are traits and whose
553 edges are significant pairwise links. Network topology highlights functional blocks where
554 traits work in concert (modules), as well as "hub" traits such as wood density in hydraulics or
555 seed mass in reproduction (Kleyer *et al.*, 2019). As the structural backbone of their respective
556 modules, hub traits anchor the physiological and ecological processes within the block,
557 shaping its overall architecture of trait coordination.

558 In contrast, ordination methods like PCA summarize relationships across modules. By
559 passing one representative variable from each network module (ideally the hub trait) into an
560 ordination, we can position species in a continuous, low-dimensional space that preserves
561 both geometry and ecological meaning (Bueno *et al.*, 2023; Laughlin, 2024).

562 We propose a sequential approach where hub traits identified by network analysis inform the
563 ordination. This strategy preserves the geometry needed for distance-based questions,
564 allowing estimation of species' position within the trait space while ensuring that no
565 functional block is under-represented and redundancy is minimized (Pan *et al.*, 2025). The
566 workflow is therefore hierarchical:

- 567 1. Partition traits into ecophysiologicaly motivated modules (organs or processes).
- 568 2. Construct a correlation network inside each module, checking that results are robust
569 across a range of correlation thresholds.
- 570 3. Select one hub trait per module and feed these variables into an ordination that defines
571 the unified space.
- 572 4. Optionally, run a global network across all traits to verify that the modules are
573 recovered or to highlight unexpected cross-links.

574 By linking detailed insights from networks with ordination's simplicity, this approach creates
575 robust trait spaces that better capture phenotypic integration and adaptation.